

<https://doi.org/10.70590/ice.2025.01.96>
<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:05346C34-1D3F-44A6-B403-F7D0EF2C61AC>

● A new species and a new record of the genus *Arria* Stål, 1877 (Mantodea: Haaniidae) from southwestern China

Ya-Fei WANG^{1,2,6#*}, Hao TANG^{3,7#}, Chen-Yao TANG^{4,8} & Hong-Lin LI^{5,9}

¹Yunnan Key Laboratory of Forest Ecosystem Stability and Global Change Response, Xishuangbanna Tropical Botanical Garden, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Mengla, Xishuangbanna 666100, China

²School of Ecology and Environmental Science, Yunnan University, Kunming 650500, China

³Department of Biology, University of Miami, Coral Gables, Florida 33146, USA

⁴College of Fisheries, Ocean University of China, Qingdao 266003, China

⁵Shala road, Menglun Town, Mengla, Xishuangbanna 666100, China

⁶ solarwang@xtbg.ac.cn

⁷ hxt402@miami.edu

⁸ 21250513049@stu.ouc.edu.cn

⁹ 1124280510@qq.com

#These authors contributed equally to this work

*Corresponding authors

Abstract: A new species of *Arria* (Mantodea: Haaniidae) from northwestern Yunnan Province, China, *A. brevicollis* sp. nov., is described. The morphology and diagnostic characters of the new species are illustrated. In addition, *A. stanleyi* Chao, 2025 is newly recorded from China for the first time. The geographic distributions of these two species in China are also presented.

Keywords: Arriini, morphology, new species, Yunnan

● 中国西南地区缺翅螳属（螳螂目：角螳科）一新种及一新纪录

王亚飞^{1,2#*}, 唐昊^{#3}, 唐晨垚⁴, & 李洪林⁵

¹中国科学院西双版纳热带植物园, 云南省森林生态系统稳定性与全球变化响应重点实验室, 西双版纳 666100, 中国

²云南大学生态与环境学院, 昆明 650500, 中国

³迈阿密大学生物学系, 迈阿密 33146, 美国

⁴中国海洋大学水产学院, 青岛 266003, 中国

⁵勐腊县勐仑镇沙腊路公租房小区 1 栋, 西双版纳 666100, 中国

#共同第一作者

*通讯作者

摘要: 本文描述了产自中国云南省西北部的缺翅螳属 *Arria* Stål, 1877 一新种, 即短胸缺翅螳 *A. brevicollis* sp. nov.。文中展示了该新种的整体形态和鉴别特征图。此外, 本文还首次记录了斯坦利缺翅螳 *A. stanleyi* Chao, 2025 在中国的分布, 并提供了以上两物种在中国的地理分布图。

关键词: 缺翅螳族, 形态学, 新物种, 云南

Accepted by Cheng-Bin WANG: 13.XII.2025; published online: 16.XII.2025

Copyright Ya-Fei WANG *et al.* This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CCBY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

● Introduction

The genus *Arria* was erected by Stål (1877), with *A. cinctipes* Stål designated as the type species. The taxonomy of the genus has recently undergone significant revision; Schwarz & Roy (2018) proposed *Palaeothespis* Tinkham 1937 and *Pseudothespis* Mukherjee 1995 as junior synonyms of *Arria*. Historically, species exhibiting morphological features similar to genus *Arria* in China have been assigned to *Palaeothespis*. Wu *et al.* (2024) noted that revision by Schwarz & Roy (2018) did not examine the male genitalia of the type species of these three genera, this taxonomic uncertainty has continued to complicate the identification of Chinese species historically assigned to *Palaeothespis*. Currently, this genus comprises 11 species distributed across eastern, southern, and southeastern Asia, including China, India, Vietnam, Thailand, and Myanmar (Schwarz & Roy 2019), with 7 species recorded in China (Wang *et al.* 2021; Wu *et al.* 2024).

The taxonomic confusion is particularly evident in the case of *Arria oreophila* (Tinkham, 1937), the first species described from China and the type species of the nominal genus *Palaeothespis*. The original description of *A. oreophila* included only hand-drawn illustrations and limited diagnostic information (Tinkham 1937). Subsequent re-examination of the type specimen (housed in the National Museum of Natural History) revealed several morphological features that differ significantly from the original description (Svenson 2014). Wang *et al.* (2021) concurred, noting that the morphological characters documented by Svenson (2014) align well with the diagnostic features of the genus *Arria*.

Ecologically, *Arria* species in China are typically associated with high-elevation habitats and, due to the apterous nature of the adult females, populations lack significant dispersal ability (Ge & Chen 2008; Zhu *et al.* 2012). This combination of factors often results in high levels of local endemism. Consequently, the Hengduan Mountains, located on the southeastern margin of the Qinghai-Tibetan Plateau, represent a critical region for understanding the genus's diversity. The area is characterized by dramatic topographic relief and a rich array of ecological niches (Xing & Ree 2017), and has been recognized in multiple syntheses as a global biodiversity hotspot (Myers *et al.* 2000; Sun *et al.* 2017; Ye *et al.* 2015). Despite their significance, mantodean diversity in this region remains insufficiently surveyed.

In this study, we describe a new species of *Arria* from the Hengduan Mountains, and we report an additional *Arria* species newly recorded from the Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region, China.

● Material and methods

Adult mantises were directly found and captured using plastic box or insect net. Specimens were euthanised with alcohol, then pinned, positioned, and air-dried. All material was stored at room temperature for subsequent examination and imaging. Specimen photographs were taken with a Canon EOS 7D digital camera fitted with a Canon 100 mm macro lens.

The classification system follows Schwarz & Roy (2019). Terminology for adult morphology follows Schwarz & Roy (2019), while male genitalia terminology adheres to Schwarz & Roy (2019), Wang *et al.* (2021) and Wu *et al.* (2024). Male genitalia were softened in 10% potassium hydroxide solution at room temperature for 24 hours, then dissected in a water-filled Petri dish to remove residual tissue. Genitalia were treated with 70% glycerol to enhance transparency and photographed using a Nikon Vihent microscope. Processed genitalia were stored in 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tubes containing 70% glycerol and retained alongside their respective specimens.

The specimens were deposited in the following institutions or private collections: KMIZ Kunming institute of zoology, Kunming, China. CWYF Collection of Ya-Fei Wang, Xishuangbanna, China.

Abbreviations

afa = phalloid apophysis; **avfs** = anteroventral femoral spines; **avts** = anteroventral tibial spines; **ce** = cercus; **CS9** = ♂ coxosternite; **ds** = discoidal spines; **ey** = compound eye; **fdl** = main posterior lobe of right phallomere; **gs**

= genicular spur; ; **L4A** = sclerite extending over the ventral wall of left phallomere; **L4B** = sclerite extending over the dorsal wall of left phallomere; **lf** = lower frons; **mz** = metazona; **oc** = ocellus; **paa** = posterior process of left phallomere; **pva** = process anteromesal to pia of right phallomere; ; **pz** = prozona; **sdpl** = lateral secondary distal process; **sl9** = stylus; **t10** = tergite 10 (= supra-anal plate); **tl** = terminal lobe of ventral phallomere in *Arria*; **ts** = tibial spur.

● Taxonomy

Arria Stål, 1877

Arria Stål, 1877: 20; Mukherjee *et al.* 1995: 277; Ehrmann 2002: 72; Schwarz & Roy 2018: 456, 2019: 141. TS: *Arria cincipes* Stål, 1877.

Palaeothespis Tinkham 1937: 497; Zhang 1987: 239; Wang 1993: 114; Ehrmann 2002: 259; Zhu *et al.* 2012: 112; Schwarz & Roy 2018: 456. syn.

Pseudothespis Mukherjee 1995: 252–253; Ehrmann 2002: 298; Schwarz & Roy 2018: 456. syn.

Arria brevicollis Wang & Tang sp. nov.

<https://zoobank.org/23163761-BFED-4AC7-AC85-0B7C84B9DD14>

Figs 1, 2, 5, 7

Type materials. Holotype. CHINA: 1♂, Yunnan, Diqing Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Weixi; 27°16'24"N, 99°27'48"E; 2499 m; 2025-VIII-13, Ya-Fei Wang *leg.* [KMIZ]. **Paratypes (nymph).** CHINA: 1♀, the same data as the holotype, but collected by Can Zhang in 2024-VII-22. [KMIZ].

Description

Body small size, robust. Male with well-developed wings, extend beyond the end of the abdomen. Female apterous, body with small granules.

Male.

Head. Triangular, about 1.7 times as wide as long. Compound eyes large, oval sized, prominently produced anterolaterally; juxta-ocular bulges low. Ocelli rounded, large, central ocellus larger than lateral ones; vertex flat. Antennae filiform, scapes tubular, inflated. Lower frons transverse, about 2.5 times as wide as high, surface flat; dorsal margin trapezoidal. Clypeus shorter than lower frons, wider than high.

Prothorax. Pronotum short, robust, surface bears sparse granules. Prozone bears two longitudinal carinae, two pairs of elevations on prozone near supracoxal sulcus, lateral to midlinekeel; supracoxal sulcus slightly expanded laterally. Pronotum length/supracoxal dilatation width ratio 1.96; metazone/prozone length ratio 1.65. Lateral margins of pronotum covered with small denticles, continuing to the base of metazone. Prosternum flat, with middle carina posteriad supracoxal sulcus.

Prothoracic legs. Short, slender. Forecoxae as long as pronotum, anterior and posterior margins bear minute denticles, posterior margin more densely serrate than the anterior. Femora long, dorsal surface with a small black tubercle, surface densely granulate, lateral margin with small tubercles; femora with 4 posteroventral, 4 discoidal, 11–12 anteroventral spines and 1 genicular spines. Tibiae slender, with irregular dark maculae; with 6 posteroventral and 7 anteroventral spines. Tarsus long, last three segments black; first joint of tarsi longer than the combined length of the remaining segments.

Meso- and metathoracic legs. Long, slender. Tibiae straight, longer than femora. Tarsus shorter than tibia, combined length of the remaining tarsal segments slightly shorter than the first segment.

Wings. Forewings long, well-developed; hyaline, with some sparsely distributed small spots; costal area long, narrow; stigma inconspicuous. Hindwings broad, with pointed apex; hyaline, with faint infumated patch.

FIGURE 1. *Arria brevicollis* sp. n.: **A, B** body in dorsal view **A** male holotype **B** female paratype.

Abdomen. Long, narrow, venter medially elevated. Cerci long, hairy, with 12 cercomeres, terminus conical; subgenital plate ventrally with numerous short setae, longer than wide, posterior margin acute, styli short, close to each other.

External genitalia. Weakly sclerotised. Ventral phallomere slender, elongate; sdpl on right side with transverse tl in ventral view, narrow and elongate; sdpl short, robust, rod-shaped, apex blunt, inclined to right; paa elongate, strongly curved, almost parallel to L4B; L1 elongate, afa strongly sclerotised. Right phallomere fda gradually narrowing towards apex, with minute setae; pva highly sclerotised, falcate.

Coloration. General brown. Head dark brown, juxtaocular bulges dark brown; ocelli hyaline, reddish-brown. Inner side of foretrochanter black; apices of femoral and tibial spines black. Meso- and metathoracic legs brown. Fore- and hindwings light brown; costal area of forewings brown.

Female.

Head. Similar to male, but larger, about 1.2 times as wide as long, surface with small granules; ocelli small, juxta-ocular bulges more developed, exceeding dorsal margin of vertex. Antennae extremely short. (specimen antennae missing)

Prothorax. Similar to male, but more robust, surface bears more granules. Prozone rugose, elevations near supracoxal sulcus more prominent; supracoxal sulcus laterally expanded. Pronotum length/supracoxal dilatation width ratio 1.78; metazone/prozone length ratio 1.28. Lateral margins of pronotum covered with denticles. Prosternum flat.

Prothoracic legs. Short, robust. Forecoxae as long as pronotum, with irregular dark maculae, bearing rows of minute denticles dorsally and ventrally, tip blackened. Femora long, dorsal surface with two black tubercles, surface

densely granulate, ventral surface with three irregular black maculae, lateral margin with small tubercles; femora with 4 posteroventral, 4 discoidal, 11 anteroventral spines and 1 genicular spines. Tibiae shorter than femora, also bearing irregular black maculae; with 6 posteroventral and 8 anteroventral spines. Tarsus short, almost entirely black; first joint of tarsi longer than the combined length of the remaining segments.

Meso- and metathoracic legs. Similar to male. Coxae robust, coxae and femora surfaces with small granules; femora inner surface black; tarsi nearly entirely black.

Abdomen. Robust, fusiform, wider than in males. All tergites except t10 with small lobes projections, surface with small granules. T10 conical. Cerci short, slightly surpassing t10.

FIGURE 2. External characters of *Arria brevicollis* sp. n., male, holotype: **A** head, frontal view **B** prothoracic legs, ventral view **C** forewings, dorsal view **D** pronotum, dorsal view **E** hind wings, dorsal view.

Coloration. General brown. Head dark brown, with several dark granules; ocelli hyaline. Lateral areas of pronotum dark; surface granules black, denticules on lateral margins also black. Dorsal surface of forecoxae with dark maculae, ventral surface with several small black spots; foretrochanter black. Forefemora with three irregular black maculae on ventral surface, located at base, apex, and tibial spur groove; foretibiae with irregular black spots,

tibial spur black; femoral and tibial spines brownish. Tarsus black. Meso- and metafemora and tibiae dark brown, ventrally black. Abdomen brown; lobes projections black.

Distribution. China (Yunnan).

Etymology. The species name *brevicollis* is derived from the Latin *brevis* (short) and *collum* (neck), referring to the relatively short prothorax of the species.

Diagnosis. The new species is very similar to *Arria oreophila*, but the pronotum is distinctly shorter. Compared with *A. oreophila*, the prozone is stouter and shorter, pronotum length/supracoxal dilatation width ratio 1.96 in new species, and 2.34 in *A. oreophila*; metazone/prozone length ratio 1.65 in new species, and 1.68 in *A. oreophila*.

The new species occurs near the distribution of *Arria pallidus* (Zhang, 1987), but can be clearly distinguished by its broader and shorter pronotum, pronotum length/supracoxal dilatation width ratio 1.96 in new species, and 2.98 in *A. pallidus*; the new species bears 11–12 anteroventral spines on the forefemora, and 6 posteroventral and 7 anteroventral spines on the foretibiae; whereas *A. pallidus* bears 13 anteroventral spines on the forefemora, and 6 posteroventral and 7 anteroventral spines on the foretibiae. Male genitalia of new species also differ from those of *A. pallidus*: by the stouter and more curved sdpl, strongly sclerotised afa, and shorter pva.

Measurements (lengths in mm).

Male. Body (head to abdomen): 29.84; pronotum: 6.10, fore coxa: 5.95; fore femora: 6.94; fore tibia: 3.19; hind femora: 7.33; hind tibia: 8.23; fore wing: 31.68; hind wing: 28.12.

Female. Body (head to abdomen): 23.39; pronotum: 6.59; fore coxa: 6.03; fore femora: 6.69; fore tibia: 4.17; hind femora: 5.79; hind tibia: 6.06.

FIGURE 3. *Arria stanleyi* Chao, 2025: **A, B** body in dorsal view **A** male **B** female.

Arria stanleyi Chao, 2025 [Newly recorded species for China]

Figs 3, 4, 6, 7

Arria stanleyi Chao, 2025: 476–484.

Materials examined. 2♂, 3♀; China, Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region, Nanning City, Shanglin County, Da'feng'zhen; 23°25'98"N, 108°32'17"E, 377 m; 15 November 2024; Chen-Yao Tang leg. [CWYF].

FIGURE 4. External characters of *Arria stanleyi*, male, **A** head, frontal view **B** prothoracic legs, ventral view **C** forewings, dorsal view **D** pronotum, dorsal view **E** hind wings, dorsal view.

Redescription.**Male.**

Medium-sized. Body green with dense black speckling. Head triangular; compound eyes globular with horizontal brown banding; ocelli large. Vertex short, smooth; juxta-ocular bulges extremely low. Lower frons wider than long; clypeus semicircular, slightly elevated; antennae filiform, longer than pronotum. Pronotum slender, highly arched on prozone with dense tubercles; metazone slightly swollen; a pair of small conical tubes at distal prozone and two larger conical tubes before supracoxal sulcus; lateral margins thin with small denticles. Fore coxae long, longer than fore femora, bearing rows of minute denticles dorsally and ventrally. Femora slender with mid-length infusate maculae; tarsi longer than tibiae. Meso- and metathoracic legs long, slender, with small ventral spines and one apical tibial spine. Forewings long, narrow, apex rounded, densely speckled; hind wings clear, truncated apically. Abdomen long and flat, tergites with acute lateral lobes; sternites smooth; subgenital plate narrow and pointed; cerci long, hairy with conical apex; styli short and approximate.

Female.

Similar to male but apterous, larger. Body mostly green with scattered black blotches. Head triangular, broader than long; compound eyes globular; ocelli small, elliptical. Vertex wide and smooth; juxta-ocular bulges slightly swollen with fine granules. Lower frons short and U-shaped; clypeus semicircular and elevated; antennae short, black. Pronotum slender, with slight swelling at posterior prozone and anterior metazone; dorsal surface of prozone densely tuberculate; pair of small conical tubes on prozone and one large tube on each side of metazone; lateral margins bearing small spines; lateral expansion diamond-shaped. Fore coxae longer than fore femora with uniform denticles; femora slim with infusate patch and similar spination pattern as male. Meso- and metathoracic legs slender, with small ventral spines and one apical tibial spine. Forewings greenish brown with heavy speckling; hind wings clear. Abdomen thick, elliptical; tergites 3–6 with large foliaceous dorsal lobes, decreasing posteriorly; lateral lobes distinct on 3–7. Ovipositor longer than supra-anal plate, triangular; supra-anal plate broad and semicircular with a distinct middorsal carina; cerci hairy with conical terminal joint.

Distribution. Vietnam (Vĩnh Phúc); China (Gungxi).

Diagnosis. Compare with congeners, *A. stanleyi* can be recognized by its slender pronotum bearing prominent pointed conical tubercles and by its moderately developed juxtaocular bulges. Females are distinguished by the absence of spines on the dorsal margin of the forecoxae and the lack of blister-like projections on the meso- and metathorax, together with reduced dorsal tergal lobes. Males possess an elongate pronotum with fewer pronotal tubercles and forecoxae lacking denticles.

Measurements (lengths in mm).

Male. Body (head to abdomen): 44.83–45.67; pronotum: 13.46–14.66, front coxa: 8.13–8.99; fore femora: 10.34–11.20; fore tibia: 4.63–5.72; hind femora: 11.73–12.61; hind tibia: 12.84–14.14; fore wing: 36.85–39.17; hind wing: 33.46–37.03.

Female. Body (head to abdomen) 39.33–42.57; pronotum: 13.04–14.78 ; fore coxa: 8.42–9.04; fore femora: 11.08–11.72; fore tibia: 6.26–6.71; hind femora: 11.68–13.29; hind tibia: 13.42–15.23.

FIGURE 5. Coxosternite, tergite 10 and cercus, male genitalia of *Arria brevicollis* sp. n., ventral view: A male genitalia B coxosternite C tergite 10 and cercus.

FIGURE 6. Coxosternite, tergite 10 and cercus, male genitalia of *Arria stanleyi*, ventral view: A male genitalia B tergite 10 and cercus C coxosternite.

FIGURE 7. Distribution map of *Arria* spp. in China. Red star represents new species.

FIGURE 8. *A. oreophila* collected from type locality. (Photos Chao Wu © SEM.)

● Discussion

The taxonomy of *Arria* in southwestern China remains confused, due to the pronounced sexual dimorphism and morphological variation among females within the same species (Wang *et al.* 2021; Wu *et al.* 2024). Examination of extensive series from multiple localities shows that female morphology is highly variable within species, leading to frequent misidentifications and the proliferation of synonyms when non-genital characters are used. Consequently, reliable species delimitation can only be achieved through the examination of male genitalia and molecular phylogenetic characters.

The Hengduan Mountains, located in northwestern Yunnan Province, China, harbor extremely high species diversity due to the complex topography characterized by numerous high mountains and deep valleys (Xing & Ree 2017). While we collected and examined large number of *Arria* specimens from Yunnan, a comprehensive revision of the genus is not currently possible due to limited material and sampling localities. The *Arria* species in Yunnan are likely more diverse and exhibit more complex evolutionary relationships than currently recognized.

As noted by Wu *et al.* (2024), *Arria qinlingensis* Wu *et al.*, 2024, and *A. leigongshanensis* (Ge & Chen, 2008) are more closely related to each other. Based on dissections and morphological examination, the morphological characters and male genitalia of *A. stanleyi* differ markedly from these two species. Moreover, *A. stanleyi* prefers low-elevation, moist, and cool habitats, distinguishing it from other known *Arria* species in China. *A. stanleyi* may represent a distinct lineage of the genus in the tropical regions of the Indochinese Peninsula.

● Acknowledgements

We sincerely thank Pro. Shao-Ji Hu (YNU) and Pro. Akihiro Nakamura (XTBG), for the support and help in research. Our thanks to Chu-Xiang Zhao (Hubei), Yi-Chen Guo (Beijing), Can Zhang (YNU), Bo-Wen Ye (Shandong), Cheng-Jun Wan (Jilin), Yi-Bo Chen (Liaoning), Shen Zhang (Jilin) for providing us of the specimens. We also thank the two reviewers, Chao Wu and Hao-Ran Gao for their careful review and valuable comments. Last but not least, we thank Bo-Tao Yan (Hainan) and Zi-Xuan Li (FAFU) for their suggestions.

● References

- Brannoch SK, Wieland F, Rivera J, Klass K-D, Béthoux O & Svenson GJ 2017: Manual of praying mantis morphology, nomenclature, and practices (Insecta, Mantodea). *ZooKeys*, 696: 1–100.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.696.12542>
- Chao M 2025: Description and Genetic Barcode of *Arria stanleyi* sp. nov. (Mantodea: Haaniidae), a new moss-mimicking mantis species from Vietnam. *Zootaxa*, 5588 (3): 476–484.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5588.3.6>
- Ehrmann R 2002: *Mantodea: Gottesanbeterinnen der Welt*. Natur und Tier-Verlag, Münster, 519 pp.
- Ge D-Y & Chen X-S 2008: Review of the genus *Palaeothespis* Tinkham (Mantodea: Thespidae), with description of one new species. *Zootaxa*, 1716 (1): 53–58.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.1716.1.5>
- Mukherjee TK, Ghosh AK & Hazra AK 1995: The mantid fauna of India (Insecta: Mantodea). *Oriental Insects*, 29 (1): 185–358.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00305316.1995.10433744>
- Myers N, Mittermeier RA, Mittermeier CG, da Fonseca GAB & Kent J 2000: Biodiversity hotspots for conservation priorities. *Nature*, 403 (6772): 853–858.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/35002501>
- Schwarz CJ & Roy R 2018: Some taxonomic and nomenclatural changes in Mantodea (Dictyoptera). *Bulletin de la Société entomologique de France*, 123 (4): 451–460.

https://doi.org/10.32475/bsef_1990

- Schwarz CJ & Roy R 2019: The systematics of Mantodea revisited: an updated classification incorporating multiple data sources (Insecta: Dictyoptera). *Annales de la Société entomologique de France (N.S.)*, 55 (2): 101–196.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00379271.2018.1556567>
- Stål C 1877: Systema Mantodeorum: Essai d'une systématisation nouvelle des Mantodées. *Bihang till Kongliga Svenska Vetenskaps-Akademiens Handlingar*, 4 (10): 1–91.
- Sun H, Zhang J-W, Deng T & Boufford DE 2017: Origins and evolution of plant diversity in the Hengduan Mountains, China. *Plant Diversity*, 39 (4): 161–166.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pld.2017.09.004>
- Svenson G 2014: The type material of Mantodea (praying mantises) deposited in the National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution, USA. *ZooKeys*, 433: 31–75.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.433.7054>
- Tinkham ER 1937: Studies in Chinese Mantidae (Orthoptera). *Lingnan Science Journal*, 16 (3): 498–499.
- Wang, T-Q 1993: *Synopsis on the Classification of Mantodea from China*. Shanghai Scientific and Technological Literature Publishing House, Shanghai, 177 pp. [王天齐 1993: 中国螳螂目分类概要. 上海科学技术出版社, 上海, 177 pp.]
- Wang Y-J, Yang L, Ye F & Chen X-S 2021: A new species of the genus *Arria* Stål, 1877 (Mantodea, Haaniidae) from China with notes on the tribe Arrini Giglio-Tos, 1919. *ZooKeys*, 1025: 1–19.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.1025.56780>
- Wu C, Zhang J-Z & Liu C-X 2024: *Arria qinlingensis* sp. n., a remarkable new praying mantis from China (Mantodea: Haaniidae). *Journal of Natural History*, 58 (9–12): 408–421.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00222933.2024.2319894>
- Xing Y-W & Ree RH 2017: Uplift-driven diversification in the Hengduan Mountains, a temperate biodiversity hotspot. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 114 (17): 3444–3451.
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1616063114>
- Ye X, Liu G-H, Li Z-S, Wang H & Zeng Y 2015: Assessing Local and Surrounding Threats to the Protected Area Network in a Biodiversity Hotspot: The Hengduan Mountains of Southwest China. *Plos One*, 10 (9) [e0138533]: 1–19.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0138533>
- Zhang G-Z 1987: A new species of the genus *Palaeothespis* Tinkham From China (Mantidae: Thespiniae). *Entomotaxonomia*, 9 (3): 239–241. [张国忠 1987: 中国古细足螳属一新种记述 (螳螂目: 螳螂科). 昆虫分类学报, 9 (3): 239–241.]
- Zhu X-Y, Wu C & Yuan Q 2012: *Mantodea in China*. Xiyuan Publishing House, Beijing, 331 pp. [朱笑愚, 吴超 & 袁勤 2012: 中国螳螂. 西苑出版社, 北京, 331 pp.]

● Additional information

Author contributions: Conceptualization: Y-F Wang. Project administration: Y-F Wang. Resources: C-Y Tang & Y-F Wang. Supervision: H Tang. Visualization: H-L Li, Y-F Wang & H Tang. Writing–original draft: Y-F Wang & H Tang. Writing–review and editing: Y-F Wang & H Tang.

Conflict of interest: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Data availability: All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

Ethical statement: No ethical statement was reported.

Funding: This study did not receive any funding.

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of *ICE* and/or the editor(s). *ICE* and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.

Citation: Wang Y-F, Tang H, Tang C-Y & Li H-L 2025: A new species and a new record of the genus *Arria* Stål, 1877 (Mantodea: Haaniidae) from southwestern China. *The Indochina Entomologist*, 1 (96): 969–981. [王亚飞, 唐昊, 唐晨垚 & 李洪林 2025: 中国西南地区缺翅螳属 (螳螂目: 角螳科) 一新种及一新纪录. 中南半岛昆虫学家, 1 (96): 969–981.]
<https://doi.org/10.70590/ice.2025.01.96>
